

INFLUENCE OF PARENT MATERIALS AND LAND USE ON SOIL CARBON SEQUESTRATION IN SOUTHERN NIGERIA

¹Ibe O. K., ²Nnaji G. U., ²Uzoma K. C. and ³Okocha O. I.

¹Department of Soil Science, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, Imo State, Nigeria

²Department of Soil Science and Land Resources Management, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, Abia State, Nigeria

³Federal College of Education, Eha Amufu, Enugu State, Nigeria

Corresponding Email: kalu.ibe@uaes.edu.ng

Phone Number: +234 803 597 7248

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18505496>

Abstract: A study was conducted to determine the effect of parent materials and land use on C sequestration in southern Nigeria. The experimental design used for the study was a 2 x 5 x 3 factorial in RCBD. The factors were land use (managed tree croplands (MTC) and continuously cultivated croplands (CCC), parent material (coastal plain sands at the Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria (FRIN), Isieke; Shale at the National Horticultural Research Institute (NIHORT), Okigwe, Imo Clay Shale at the Anambra-Imo River Basin Development Authority (AIRBDA), Agbala; Coastal Plain sands at the Niger Delta Basin Development Authority (NDBDA), Kpong and Alluvium at the Niger Delta Basin Development Authority (NDBDA), Isiokolo and soil horizon depths (0-19, 20-39 and 40-100 cm). Physical properties ranged from 49-85 %, 9-40 %, 4-22 % and 1.35-2.15 gcm⁻³ for sand, clay, silt and bulk density in MTC and 60-81 %, 9-30 %, 5-13 % and 1.38-2.15 gcm⁻³ for sand, clay, silt and bulk density in CCC. The textural class ranged from loamy sand to sandy loam at the surface and sandy clay loam to sandy clay at the subsurface. Soil reaction were extremely acid to strongly acid (pH 4.4-5.5) for MTC and very strongly acid to moderately acid (pH 4.5-5.6) for CCC. Soils under MTC sequestered higher (p<0.05) amount of C across the soil depths relative to arable croplands. SOC pool in MTC soil was within the ideal range for mitigating climate change and environmental quality control, whereas CCC land utilization type was below the threshold level. Coastal plain sands of FRIN- Isieke had highest (p<0.05) amount of SOC pool (575.80 MgCha⁻¹), while the alluvial soils of NDBDA- Isiokolo gave the lowest (409. 50 MgCha⁻¹). The study revealed that SOC sequestration is a function of land use, parent material and depth. Therefore, the soil conservation practices associated with CCC under the different parent materials in the studied area should be re-evaluated, this is because reduction of SOC in CCC increased oxidation of SOM, thereby leading to SOC losses to the atmosphere and this may also accelerate global warming.

Keywords: Soil organic carbon sequestration, Land use systems, Parent material, Soil depth, Southern Nigeria soils

Introduction

Agricultural soils are among the planet's largest reservoirs of carbon and hold potential for expanded carbon sequestration, and this, provide prospective way of enhancing aggregate stability and mitigate the increasing atmospheric concentration of CO₂ (Ibe, 2021). But, the development of Agriculture during the past centuries and particularly in last decades has entailed depletion of substantive soil carbon stocks (Nnaji, 2008; Ibe, 2014; Lal, 2017).

The impact of organic carbon (OC) losses in soils may have a variety of serious environmental consequences. Abah and Petja (2017) reported that several depletion of SOC degrades soil quality, reduces biomass productivity and adversely impacts water quality. Salako (2015) observed that organic matter (OM) losses from soil worldwide contribute to increased atmospheric CO₂ concentration. Ibe (2021) indicated that the net losses of SOC due to land use changes may occur as a result of decreased organic residue inputs and changes in litter composition, and increased rates of soil organic decomposition and soil erosion. The contribution of soil erosion to global C emission has also been recognized by Abdres *et al.* (2016) as equally important to that of deforestation and fossil fuel burning. It was estimated that the total SOC displaced by water erosion globally is 57 PgCyr⁻¹ (Aliero, 2018; Lal, 2004; and Li *et al.*, (2010). It was predicted by Lal (1996) that CO₂ emission to the atmosphere would increase from 7.4 GtCyr⁻¹ in 1997 to approximately 26 GtCyr⁻¹ by 2010. Furthermore, the annual CO₂ flux from the soil to the atmosphere (68 PgCyr⁻¹) is 11.3 times the emission from fossil fuel combustion (6 PgCyr⁻¹) (An *et al.*, 2010; and

Abdullahi *et al.*, 2018). The intergovernmental panel on climate change (IPCC, 2016) recognized three main options for the mitigation of atmospheric CO₂ concentration by the agricultural sector:

- i) Reduction of agriculture-related emissions
- ii) Creation and strengthening of C sinks in the soil and
- iii) Production of bio-fuels to replace fossil fuels

There is need to evaluate the role of parent material and land use in the distribution of organic C and N among labile and stable pools with kinetically different turnover rates. This will help in the enhancement of soil fertility and stability of soil micro aggregates. It is with this background that several attempts have been made to assess the potential of coastal plain sands, alluvium and Imo clay shale under managed tree croplands (Ibe, 2021), sandstones under arable cropping (Salako, 2015; Ibe, 2014), shale under mixed cropping system (Anikwe, 2010) and Alluvium, Coastal plain sands and upper coal measure under cassava/maize long term cultivation (Lal and Okigbo, 1990) to sequester C as possible strategies to curtail the rate of increase of atmospheric concentration of CO₂.

According to Abdullahi *et al.* (2018), biomass production which is an important determination of C pool and fluxes depends on parent material, land use and cultural practices. Consequently, conservation of natural (TRF and TS) ecosystems to agricultural land use (plantation, pastoral and crop land) under a given parent material, has a drastic impact on C pool and emissions of GHGs to the atmosphere. Awelewa and Ogban (2017) showed that parent material and land use influence soil moisture status, soil temperature, oxygen supply (drainage), soil acidity, soil nutrient supply and clay content which are the major

environmental factors that control the behaviour of OM in the soil. Govers *et al.* (2013) also remarked that the soil forming factors, notably parent material as well as local biological activity in which human are often a predominating factor, control the amount of SOM that corresponds with equilibrium conditions in a certain natural ecosystem. Different factors influence different SOC pools. Free OM particles and microbial biomass in soils are controlled by residue inputs (management of crop residue and mulching) and climate for example, the microbial populations and activities in pasture tends to be higher compared to the corresponding agricultural soils due to the positive impacts of the surface cover, vegetation, below ground C allocation via roots and lack of tillage of pasture (FAO, 2017).

More so, soil aggregation, texture and parent material control OM in microaggregates. The other pools are less influence by agronomic factors but mainly by pedological factors-microaggregates, clay composition (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2015). Furthermore, the turnover and cycling of SOC is more rapid in the tropics than in temperate regions (Salako, 2015).

Lal (2017) reported high SOC pool in soils formed from shale with its associated increased clay contents relative to coastal plain sands with its associated low clay content. Li *et al.* (2010) recorded that soils with high activity clay have more SOC content than those with low activity clay based on the differences in their pedology.

Quantification of the impacts of parent material, land use and soil cultural/management practices on carbon stocks in southern Nigeria is challenging because of the spatial heterogeneity of soil, climate, cultural/management conditions and due to the lack of

data on soil carbon pools of most common agroecosystems. Some available statistics are generally based on extrapolation. Lal (2005) and FAO (2017) reported that the rates of SOC sequestration in agricultural and restored ecosystems range from 0 to 150 kg Cha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ in dry and warm regions and 100-1000 kgCha⁻¹yr⁻¹ in humid and cool climates. They also estimated the total potential of C sequestration in world soils as 0.4-1.2 GtCyr⁻¹, all of which were derived from natural resource inventory without special consideration of specific geological materials as a soil forming factor.

Improvement in the data base on the concentration of SOC needed to be validated with ground truth measurement/assessment, as the use of reliable data is essential for developing technique of soil management and identifying policy options needed for promoting appropriate measures. Despite several studies carried out on the quantification of soil sequestered C in different geographical and geological regions of the world (Hamed *et al.*, 2019; Bhunia *et al.*, 2016; FAO, 2017 and IUSS Working Group WRB, 2015), there are limited knowledge about SOC pool dynamics in the tropical humid agroecosystem of southern Nigeria. It is important to generate information which is essential for developing techniques of C sequestration for sustainable agriculture and erosion control leading to advancement in food security and consequently, mitigate global warming using five (5) locations in the southern agro-ecological zones of Nigeria. The aim of this study is to evaluate the influence of parent materials and land use on soil carbon sequestration in Southern Nigeria. This aim will be achieved through the following specific objectives: to:

- i) determine the effect of parent material and land use on selected soil physico-chemical properties
- ii) determine the effect of parent materials and land use on soil organic C pool.

Materials and methods

Description of the Study Area

Geographically, southern Nigeria refers to the area bounded within latitudes 10°28' north of the equator and longitude 5°25' and 8°51' east of the Greenwich meridian, occupying a land area of about 282,672.48 km² or about 30.6 % of the total land area of Nigeria. It represents about 75.02 million or 39.3% of the

population of Nigeria (Monanu, 1975, and Ofomata, 1975, Lal and Okigbo, 1990; Abia State Official Gazette, 1992). The study was conducted at the Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria (FRIN) Isieke, National Horticultural Research Institute (NIHORT) Okigwe, Anambra-Imo River Basin Development Authority (AIRBDA) Agbala, Niger Delta Basin Development Authority (NDBDA) Kpong and Niger Delta Basin Development Authority (NDBDA) Isiokolo, in the States of Abia, Imo, Rivers and Delta, southern Nigeria (Figure 1).

Map of southern Nigeria showing the study location

Geology, climate and natural vegetation of the study area

The soils of FRIN-Isieke are derived from coastal plain sands of Bende Ameki formation (Lekwa and Whiteside, 1986; Nuga and Akinbola, 2011). Soils of NIHORT-Okigwe are derived from shale of Ajali formation (Jungerius, 1964; Ojanuga, 1977). While soils of AIRBDA-Agbala are underlain by Imo Clay Shale of Imo formation of the tertiary period. The residuum of this shale formation is the parent material of the soils (Asadu et al., 1997; Ojanuga, 1998). Soils of NDBDA-Kpong are derived from coastal plain sands of Benin formation. The coastal plain sands are connected with the sea with a large number of creeks. The general geology of the area essentially reflects the influence of movement of rivers in the Niger Delta, in their search for lines of flow to the sea with consequent deposition of transported sediments (Lekwa and Whiteside, 1986; FDALR, 1990). Whereas, the soils of NDBDA-Isiokolo are derived from Alluvium. The geology of the area is quaternary to recent alluvium known as the sombreiro (Deltaic plain sands, clayey/silty sand) (Jungerius, 1964; Ojanuga *et al.*, 1981; FDALR, 1990). The geomorphology of the five (5) locations is nearly level to gently undulating (0-3 %) and the altitude ranged from 14 masl to 182 masl (Lal and Okigbo, 1990; FDALR, 1990; Ojanuga, 1998; Ibe, 2021). The drainage of the area encompasses the entire land surface dissected and drained by many streams and creeks that flow in southerly direction into one another and eventually into the Atlantic coastal marshes (Lekwa and Whiteside, 1986; Ibe, 2014; Nwagbara and Ibe, 2015; Osodeke, 2017).

The southern Nigeria has a tropical humid climate with bimodal rainfall distribution pattern but with less

intensity and clear distribution between wet and dry seasons in the tropical rainforest (Abia and Imo State). The freshwater swamp and the tropical rainforest have average rainfall of 2500 mm and 2350 mm, respectively (Nwagbara and Ibe, 2015; NIMET, 2018). Air temperature in southern Nigeria are generally high all year round. Mean minimum temperature of the area is 35°C while the mean minimum is 21°C, given an annual range of about 11°C (Nuga and Akinbola, 2011; NIMET, 2018). The study area is endowed with an annual average daily sunshine hours of 6.25 hours ranging from 3.5 hours at the coastal area to 9.0 hours at the far northern boundary. The minimum and maximum hours of sunshine amount to 0.1 and 9.9 hours, respectively (Uguru et. al., 2011; NIMET, 2018). Similarly, it has an annual daily solar radiation of about 2.25 Kwh/m²/day varying between 3.5 Kwh/m²/day at the coastal areas and 7.0 Kwh/m²/day at the northern boundary. Relative humidity over the study ranged from 65 % to 92 % at the coastal area through 82 % in the central area (Chikezie et. al., 2016; NIMET, 2018).

The vegetation of the experimental area is typical of tropical rainforest vegetation. The secondary bush which dominates the area are the remnants of the tropical rainforests which are fast disappearing in the area. Some of the forest species found in the area especially in the ally crop portion include: oil bean (*Pentaclethra marcophyllum*), oil pam (*Elaeis guinensis*), plaintain/ banana (*Musa spp*), raffia palm (*Raphia spp*). Grasses and broadleaf weeds that dominate the entire area include *Panicum maximum*, *Pennisetum purperium*, *Cyperus spp*, *Axonopus compressus*, *Elusime indica*, *Chromolaena odoratum*,

Centroceema pubescence, *Culapgonium mucunoides* and *Aspillia africana*.

The experimental sites had been cropped continuously for more than ten years for arable crops with mechanical clearing done in February/March followed by panting in April/May. During these years, there were intercropping systems in some areas. Inorganic fertilizer were used. Weeding were done manually with hoes, cutlass and trowels. Also, there were herbicides applications. There were longer stand rotation in the horticultural and managed forest tree plantations.

Stratified random sampling as modified by Smith (1976), was used in the collection of soil sample. Six (6) mini-pits of the same dimensions (0.5 m x 0.5 m x 1 m) were dug in sample locations and sample collected at depths 0 -19, 20- 39, 40-100 cm. The mini-pits were dug to represent landscapes occupied by different tree and arable crops under define management and cultural practices over a long period of time. Within each sampling location, soils of similar textures were collected from intensive arable cropland adjacent to the tree cropland (horticultural tree crops, plantations and managed forest ecosystem) in each location. In general, soils under 8 (LUTs) were studied. Three sites (replicates) in each location were chosen for collection of soil samples to represent each of the LUTs. A total of 90 soil samples were collected from the five locations at three depths from each sample site. The land utilization types were: (1) *Pinus carribean* plantation (PPF-PCP) at FRIN-Isieke (2) *Irvingia wombulu* Plantation (MTC-IWPN) NIHORT- Okigwe (3) *Elias guineensis* plantation (MTC-OPP) at AIRBDA-Agbala (4) *Musa paradisiaca* plantation (MTC-PPk) at NDBDA- Kpong and (MTC-PPI) NDBDA-Isiokolo (5)

Cassava/Maize/*Telferia* Intercrop (CCC-CMTF) at FRIN-Isieke and (CCC-CMTI) NDBDA-Isiokolo (6) Cassava/Maize/Okra Intercrop (CCC-CMO) at AIRBDA-Agbala (7) Cassava/Maize/Yam Intercrop (CCC-CMY) at NDBDA-Kpong (8) Cassava/Maize/Melon Intercrop (CCC-CMM) at NIHORT-Okigwe.

Information on land use and cultural practices were derived from farm management and crop production reports and cultural practices of AIRBDA- Agbala, forest cultural practice guide of FRIN-Isieke, research collaboration and training reports of NDBDA for Kpong and Isiokolo project sites, and records of farming system research programme of NIHORT-Okigwe were used. Also, information were acquired from interviews with heads of station of the collaborating institutions, heads of units and technical officers.

Laboratory analysis

Particle size distribution was determined by the hydrometer method as described by Gee and Bander (1986). Bulk density was obtained by the cylindrical core method as described by Blacke and Hantge (1986). Soil pH was determined in distilled water and Potassium Chloride solution at ratio 1:1 and 1:2.5 soil/water suspension using pH meter (McClean, 1982). Soil organic carbon content was quantified by Walkley and Black wet oxidation method as described by Nelson and Sommers (1982). Total nitrogen content was determined by the macrokjeldahl digestion method using CUSO₄ and NaSO₄ catalyst mixture (Bremmer and Mulvaney, 1982). Cation exchange capacity (CEC) was determined by the NH₄OAC (Ammonium acetate) pH method (Thomas, 1982). Available Phosphorus was determined using Bray and Kurtz II solution (Olsen and Sommers,

1982). The SOC pool content was calculated using the equation of Lal *et al.* (1998):

$$\text{MgCha}^{-1} = \frac{(\% \text{ C} \times \text{Pb} \times \text{d} \times 10^{-4} \text{m}^2 \text{ha}^{-1})}{100}$$

100

Where; MgCha⁻¹ = Megagram carbon per hectare (1 Mg = 10⁶g), % C = percentage of C given by laboratory results, Pb = Soil bulk density (Megagram per cubic meters), d = depth in meters

Statistical Analysis

The experimental design used for the study was a 2 x 5 x 3 factorial in randomized complete block design (RCBD). The factors were land use [managed tree croplands (MTC) and continuously cultivated croplands (CCC)], parent material [coastal plain sands at the Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria (FRIN)], Isieke; Shale at the National Horticultural Research Institute (NIHORT), Okigwe; Imo Clay Shale at the Anambra-Imo River Basin Development Authority (AIRBDA), Agbala; Coastal Plain Sands at the Niger Delta Basin Development Authority (NDBDA), Kpong and Alluvium at the Niger Delta Basin Development Authority (NDBDA), Isiokolo and depth (0-19, 20-39 and 40-100 cm). The data collected on the various parameters were analyzed using ANOVA. Separation of treatment means for significant difference was performed by the FLSD procedure according to Obi (1986).

Results and Discussion

Soil physico-chemical characterization

The particle size analyses of the soil showed that the sand particles are the dominant size fraction in both major land utilization types ranging from 49-85 % in MTC and 66-81 % in CCC. While clay particles ranged from 9-40 % in MTC and 9-30 % in CCC. Whereas silt fractions were the least with values

ranging from 4-22 % and 5-13 % MTC and CCC respectively. The textural class generally ranged from loamy sand to sandy loam at the surface and sandy clay loam to sandy clay at the subsurface horizons. Bulk density values ranged from 1.35-2.15 gcm⁻³ and 1.38-2.15 gcm⁻³ in MTC and CCC respectively. This is in alignment with the findings of Ogumwole *et al.* (2014), who recorded high bulk density in soils with high clay content.

The soils were extremely acid to strongly acid (pH 4.4-5.5) in soils under MTC and very strongly acid to moderately acid (pH 4.5-5.6) in soils under CCC. The organic carbon content ranged from 1.57-3.80 % and 0.37-3.56 % in soils under MTC and CCC respectively. Organic carbon content of the two major LUTS were within the optimal range (3-5 %) as reported by FAO (2017), except in soils under CCC. The depletion of SOC in soils under CCC could be due to long term continuous cultivation, vegetation removal and tillage operation.

Available phosphorus across the major LUTs ranged from moderate to high for MTC (13.80-28.07 mgkg⁻¹) and CCC (9.03-26.67 mgkg⁻¹) and varied down the profile. This could be due to prolonged accumulation of SOM resulting from litter fall and debris of organic material in the managed tree croplands and constant application of chemical fertilizer (NPK) in the continuous cultivated croplands. Research findings in confirmation to this abound in literature (Nzegbule, 2018; Asawalam, 2017; Baishya, 2015). However, Osodeke (2017) contradicted this observation. The range for K was very low (0.01-0.19 cmolkg⁻¹) and very low to moderate (0.02-0.62 cmolkg⁻¹) in soils under MTC and CCC respectively.

Suliman *et al.* (2019) and Yadav and Arora (2018) reported that soils with underlying clays have much

higher levels of cations than surface soils. Whereas Anikwe (2010) recorded that the low level of basic cations in soils are reflection of low pH which affect nutrient solubility and sorption. Cation exchange capacity (CEC) ranged from moderate to high (14.20-26.28 cmolkg⁻¹ for MTC and moderate (10.81-18.60 cmolkg⁻¹) for CCC. Total nitrogen ranged from low to very high (0.07-0.51 %) in MTC and very low to very

high (0.04-0.40 %) in CCC. Soil organic carbon pool across the LUTs ranged from 33.80-326.80 mgCha⁻¹ in soils under MTC and 17.80-197.80MgCha⁻¹ in soils under CCC. This is in line with the findings of Eibasiouny *et al.* (2014), Khera and Singh (2008), who recorded higher sequestration of soil organic carbon in soils under managed tree croplands relative to continuously cultivated croplands (Table 1 and 2).

Table 1: Mean values of physico-chemical properties of soil under managed tree croplands (MTC)

Parent material	Land use	Depth (cm)	%			Textural Class	BD (g/cm ³)	pH (H ₂ O)	%		cmolkg ⁻¹		P (mgKg ⁻¹)	SOC Pool
			Sand	Clay	Silt				SO C	TN	K	CEC		
CPS-FRIN-ISIEKE	PPF-PCP	0-19	75	9	16	SL	1.48	5.50	3.63	0.5	0.0	18.0	15.25	133.40
		20-39	71	11	18	SL	1.58	4.90	3.28	0.3	0.0	16.1	19.75	107.60
		40-100	69	3	28	SCL	1.78	4.60	3.28	0.3	0.0	16.1	13.80	334.80
SHL-NIHORT-OKIGWE	MTC-IWP	0-19	75	14	11	SL	1.62	5.0	2.11	0.1	0.0	25.0	18.33	88.00
		20-39	65	22	13	SL	1.81	5.5	3.10	0.2	0.0	22.0	18.33	104.10
		40-100	49	11	40	SC	1.84	5.5	3.06	0.3	0.2	22.0	19.26	326.80
ICS-AIRBDA-AGBALA	MTC-OPP	0-19	75	12	13	LS	1.50	4.9	3.80	0.0	0.6	26.2	28.07	102.10
		20-39	73	10	17	SL	1.63	4.9	3.40	0.0	0.0	23.1	19.10	111.80
		40-100	71	4	25	SCL	1.68	4.8	3.20	0.0	0.0	24.0	17.03	313.80
CPS-NDBDA-KPONG	MTC-PP _k	0-19	77	10	13	SL	1.33	4.702	2.60	0.1	0.0	20.1	19.37	72.50
		20-39	77	6	17	SL	1.33	4.40	2.80	0.1	0.0	17.0	16.07	73.80

		40-100	79	6	15	SL	1.50	4.70	1.80	0.0	0.0	16.8	17.27	172.20
ALV-NDBDA-ISIOKOLO	MTC-PP ₁	0-19	85	6	9	LS	1.41	4.78	3.56	0.1	0.1	18.5	20.00	95.60
		20-39	75	10	15	SL	1.85	4.79	2.84	0.1	0.1	14.2	17.00	96.00
		40-100	75	4	21	SCL	2.15	4.82	1.57	0.1	0.1	15.2	15.10	217.90

Keys:

BD=Bulk density, CEC=Cation Exchange Capacity, TN=Total Nitrogen, SOC=Soil Organic Carbon, P=Phosphorus, K= Potassium, LUT=Land Utilization type, CPS-FRIN-ISIEKE=Coastal plain sand of forestry research institute of Nigeria, Isieke; SHL-NIHORT-Okigwe=shale of national horticultural research institute, Okigwe; ICS-AIRBDA-AGBALA=Imo clay shale of anambra-imo river basin development authority, Agbala; CPS-NDBDA-KPONG=Coastal plain sands of niger delta basin development authority, Kpong; ALV-NDBDA-ISIOKOLO=alluvium of niger delta basin development authority, Isiokolo; PPF-PCP=Planted pine forest of pinus caribae plantation; MTC-IWP=managed tree cropland of irvingia wombulu plantation; MTC-OPP= managed tree cropland of oil palm plantation; MTC-PPk/MTC-PPi=managed tree cropland of plantain plantation

Table 2: Mean Values of physico-chemical properties of soils under continuously cultivated croplands (CCC)

Parent material	Land use	Dept h (cm)	% Sand Silt Clay			Textural Class	BD (g/cm ³)	pH (H ₂ O)	% SOC TN		cmolkg ⁻¹ K CE C P (mgKg-1)			SOC Pool
			Sand	Silt	Clay				SOC	TN	K	CE	C	
CPS-FRIN-ISIEKE	CCC-CMT _F	0-19	79	11	10	SL	1.56	5.6	1.31	0.25	0.04	11.1	18.33	33.80
		20-39	75	7	18	SL	1.38	5.2	1.34	0.11	0.08	10.8	20.00	31.70
		40-100	66	5	30	SCL	1.66	4.9	0.80	0.34	0.01	12.1	26.67	58.20
SHL-NIHORT-OKIGWE	CCC-CMM	0-19	77	12	11	SL	1.70	4.7	0.87	0.13	0.05	13.0	26.63	27.80
		20-39	65	7	18	SL	1.88	4.9	0.57	0.40	0.05	16.0	18.54	23.60
		40-100	60	13	27	SCL	2.05	5.1	1.03	0.13	0.04	12.0	16.38	98.70
ICS-AIRBDA-AGBALA	CCC-CMO	0-19	80	5	15	SL	1.68	4.5	1.80	0.04	0.08	18.6	23.83	37.20
		20-39	70	5	21	SCL	1.62	4.8	0.91	0.13	0.07	16.4	21.32	26.60
		40-100	71	8	21	SCL	1.93	4.7	0.80	0.14	0.06	13.6	15.27	87.50
CPS-NDBDA-KPONG	CCC-CMY	0-19	81	8	11	LS	1.56	4.66	0.95	0.18	0.10	16.1	10.37	21.40
		20-39	77	6	17	SL	1.66	4.87	0.59	0.09	0.11	13.1	13.27	17.80
		40-100	78	7	15	SL	1.90	4.53	0.57	0.10	0.09	13.0	9.03	61.80
ALV-NDBDA-ISIOKOLO	CCC-MMT _I	0-19	80	11	9	LS	1.70	4.78	3.56	0.11	0.09	18.0	22.00	56.40
		20-39	80	9	11	SL	1.72	4.95	2.84	0.13	0.09	14.8	15.00	62.60
		40-100	75	8	17	SL	2.15	4.82	1.57	0.10	0.12	13.1	16.00	197.80

Keys:

BD=Bulk density, CEC=Cation Exchange Capacity, TN=Total Nitrogen, SOC=Soil Organic Carbon, P=Phosphorus, K=Potassium, LUT=Land Utilization type; CCC- CMTf/CCC-CMTi= continuously cultivated cropland of cassava/maize/telfetia; CCC-CMM= continuously cultivated cropland of cassava/maiz/melon;CCC-CMY=continuously cultivated cropland of cassava/maize/yam; CPS-FRIN-ISIEKE= coastal plain sands of the forestry research institute of Nigeria, Isieke; SHL-NIHORT-OKIGWE=shale of national institute of horticultural research institute,;Okigwe; ICS-AIRBDA-AGBALA= Imo clay shale of anambra imo river basin development authority, Agbala; CPS-NDBDA-KPONG= coastal plain sands of Niger delta basin development authority, Kong; ALV-NDBDA-ISIOKOLO=Alluvium of Niger delta basin development authority, Isiokolo

Soil Organic Carbon Pool

The effects of parent material, land use and depth on SOC pool under MTC and CCC across the study area are presented in Table 3. Significant ($p<0.05$) influence of parent material on SOC pool was observed across the study area with SOC pool of 111.10 MgCha⁻¹, 111.50 MgCha⁻¹, 113.20 MgCha⁻¹, 69.90 MgCha⁻¹ and 11.00 MgCha⁻¹ for CPS-FRIN-Isieke, SHL-NIHORT-Okigwe, ICS-AIRBDA-Agbala, CPS-NDBDA-Kpong, ALV-NDBDA-Isiokolo parent materials respectively. This suggests that SOC pool in alluvial soils were within the ideal range in relation to mitigating climate change and for better environmental quality control as postulated by FAO (2017) for surface soil (0-100 cm). Significant

($p<0.05$) influence of land use on SOC pool was observed at the three soil depths across the study area with MTC having higher SOC pool than CCC soils. The mean SOC pool were 154.50 mgCha-1 for MTC and 56.20 MgCha-1 for CCC soil. These results imply that MTC improved SOC pool whereas CCC degraded it. The SOC pool in MTC soil was within the ideal range (≥ 120 mgCha-1) in relation to mitigating climate change and for better environmental quality control. Significant ($p<0.05$) influence of depth on SOC pool were observed at the various depths with SOC pool varying with depth in MTC, CCC and parent materials across the study area. The highest (334.80 mgCha⁻¹) SOC Pool was observed at 40-100 cm soil depth under CPS-FRIN-Isieke followed by 326.80 mgCha⁻¹ SOC pool under SHL-NIHORT-Okigwe. The least (17.80 mgCha⁻¹) was observed at 20-39cm depth under CPS-NDBD-Kpong parent material which has been under >20 years of conventional tillage operation. This study revealed that there was greater soil carbon accumulation in forest soils when compared with arable soil irrespective of lithological differences. This result is in line with Lal (2017) who noted high SOC pool in soils under tropical forest. Significant ($P<0.05$) influence of the interaction of parent material, land use and depth was observed on SOC pool. This suggests that SOC pool is a function of land use, parent material and depth and their interactions. This result is in line with lal (2005) and li *et al.* (2010), who reported that SOC pool depends on land use and depth.

Table 3: Effect of parent materials, land use and depth on SOC pool (MgCha⁻¹) under MTC and CCC across the study area

Parent Material	Land Use
-----------------	----------

	Depth (cm)	MTC	CCC	Mean	Sub mean
CPS-FRIN-ISIEKE	0-19	100.40	33.80	67.10	
	20-39	107.60	31.70	69.60	
	40-100	334.80	58.20	196.50	
Sub mean		180.90	41.20		111.10
S-NIHORT-OKIGWE	0-19	88.00	27.80	57.90	
	20-39	104.10	23.60	63.90	
	40-100	326.80	98.70	212.70	
Sub mean		172.90	50.00		111.50
ICS-AIRBDA-AGBALA	0-19	102.10	37.20	69.70	
	20-39	111.80	26.60	69.20	
	40-100	313.80	87.50	200.70	
Sub mean		175.90	50.40		113.20
CPS-NDBDA-KPONG	0-19	72.50	21.40	46.90	
	20-39	73.80	17.80	45.80	
	40-100	172.20	61.80	117.00	
Sub mean		106.20	33.70		69.90
A-NDBDA-ISIOKOLO	0-19	95.60	56.40	76.00	
	20-39	96.00	62.60	79.30	
	40-100	217.90	197.80	207.80	
Sub mean		136.50	105.60		121.00
Total mean		154.50	56.20		
LSD_(0.05) for parent material					9.85**
LSD_(0.05) for land use					17.48*
LSD_(0.05) for depth					10.94**
LSD_(0.05) for parent material x land use					15.56**
LSD_(0.05) for parent material x depth					17.98**
LSD_(0.05) for land use x depth					15.51**
LSD_(0.05) for parent material x land use x depth					25.53**

Key:

*, ** = Significant at 0.01 and 0.05 alpha level (2 tailed), respectively, NS = Non-significant, MTC = Managed tree croplands, CCC = Continuously cultivated croplands, CPS=FRIN-Isieke =Coastal plain seeds at FRIN-Isieke, S-NIHORT-Okigwe=Shale at NIHORT-Okigwe, ICS-AIRBDA-Agbala=Imo, Clay Shale at AIRBDA-Agbala, CPS-NDBDA-Kpong=Coastal plain seeds at NDBDA-Kpong, A-NDBDA-Isokolo=Alluvium at NDBDA-Isiokolo

Conclusion

The influence of parent materials and land use on soil carbon sequestration was evaluated in southern Nigeria. Soils under managed tree croplands (MTC) sequestered higher ($p < 0.05$) amount across the soil depths relative to the continuous cultivated croplands (CCC). Coastal plain sands of FRIN- Isieke had highest amount of SOC pool. While the alluvial soils of NDBDA -Isiokolo gave the lowest. Amongst the managed tree crop LUTs, C sequestration followed this trend: Pine forest > Oil palm plantation > Irvingia Wombulu > Plantain plantation. The SOC pool in MTC soil was within the ideal range for mitigating

REFERENCES

Abah, R. C. and Petja, B. M. (2017).Crop suitability mapping for rice, cassava, and Yam in North Central Nigeria.*Journal of Agricultural Science*, 9(1)96-98.

Abdres, G. D., Raman, B., Luciano, G., Artenio, C., Paulo, P. and Agara, N. (2016). Carbon input threshold for soil carbon budget optimization in eroding vineyards. *Geoderma*, 271,144-149.

Abdullahi, A. C., Siwar, C., Shaharudin, M. and Anizan, I. (2018). Carbon sequestration in

climate change and environmental quality control, whereas CCC land utilization type was below the threshold level. Pine forest, Oil palm, *Irvingia wombulu* and Plantain plantation soils sequestered more carbon across the soil depths and therefore hold a consideration promise for carbon sequestration in southern Nigeria. The study revealed that SOC sequestration is a function of land use, parent material and depth. Therefore, the conservation practices associated with CCC under the different parent materials in the studied area should be re-evaluated. This is because reduction of SOC in CCC increased oxidation of SOM, thereby leading to SOC losses to the atmosphere and this may also accelerate global warming. Also, they are inadequate to maintain the qualities of the soils on sustainable basis with special emphasis on organic matter content. Some practices such as no-till reduced tillage, use of cover crops, mulching, application of organic and inorganic fertilizers and reduced application of agro-chemicals should be incorporated into the soil management and cultural practices.

soils: the opportunities and challenges. <http://dx.doi.org/10.57721> in technopen. 79347.

Abia State Official Gazette (1992). Official Gazette of 13th November, 1992. Bulletin 52, Vol. 79.

Ahawiwe, M. O., Nwaigbo, L. C. and Ano, A. O. (2010). Influence of plant prunnings on soil properties and yield of yam miniset. *Journal of Agriculture and Social Research (JASR)*, 10(2)1-6.

- Aliero, M. M. (2018). Assessing soil physical properties variability and their impact on vegetation using geospatial tool in Kebbi State, Nigeria. *Earth and Environmental Science*, 169:01211.
- An, S. S., Mentier, A., Mayer, H. and Bium, W. E. H. (2010). Soil aggregation, aggregate stability, organic carbon and nitrogen in different soil aggregate fractions under forest and shrub vegetation on the Loess Plateau China. *Catena*, 81:226-33.
- Anikwe, M..A. (2010). Carbon storage in soils of southeastern Nigeria under different management practices. *Carbon Balance and Management*, 5.5.Pp. 7.
- Asadu, C. L.A., Okorji, E. C. and Onah, F. O. (1997). Edaphic, Socioeconomic and cultural changes due to irrigated rice cultivation in eastern Nigeria. *Global Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences* 3 (1) Pp 3-8.
- Asawalam, D. O. (2017). Stewardship of soil: perspective of a soil fertility scientists. 8th inaugural lecture. Michael Okpara university of Agriculture, Umudike. 11th October, 2017, Pp. 64.
- Awelewa, A. E. and Ogban, I. P. (2017). Effect of intensive vegetable cultivation on soil organic carbon storage in Akwa Ibom State, Southeastern Nigeria. *British Journal of Environment and Climate Change*. ISSN:2231-4784, Vol. 5, Issue 4.
- Baishya, K. (2015). Impact of agrochemicals application soil quality degradation. A Review, 2nd International Conference on Science, Technology and Management, University of Delhi (DU), Conference Centre, New Delhi (India).
- Bhumia, G. S., Shit, P. K. and Maiti, R. (2016). *Journal of the Saudi Society of Agricultural Sciences*. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jssas.2016-02.001](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jssas.2016.02.001).
- Blake, G. R. and Harige, K. H. (1986). Bulk density In: Klute, A. (ed). *Methods of soils analysis, Part 1: American Society of Agronomy: Madison, WISC, Pp. 363-382.*
- Bremner, J. M. and Mulvaney, G. S. (1982). Nitrogen total In: Page, A. L., Miller, R. H. and Keeney, Dr (eds) *methods of soils analysis. Part 2: American Society of Agronomy, No. 9. Madison WIS. Pp. 595-624.*
- Chikezie, C. Ibekwe, U. C. Ohajianya, D. O., Orebiyi, J. O. Henry-Ukoha, A., Ukoha, I. I., Osuji, M.N., and Anthony G. (2016). Climate change and perceived climate hazard: A trend analysis in southern Nigeria. *International Journal of Weather, Climate Change and Conservation and Research*. Vol.2. No 1. Pp 1-10
- Elbasiouny, H., Abowaly, M., Abu-Alkheir, A. and Gad, A. (2014). *Catena*. 113: 76-78.
- Enwezor, W. O., Ohiri, A. C., Opuwaribo, E. E. and Udo, E. P. (1990). Climate of southeastern Nigeria. In: *Literature review on soil fertility*

- investigation in Nigeria. Federal Ministry of Agriculture and National Resources, Lagos.
- FAO (2017). Soil organic carbon: the hidden potential. Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations Rome, Italy.
- FDALR (1990). The Reconnaissance Soil Survey of Nigeria. Soil Report. Vol. 5. FDALR, Kaduna, Nigeria.
- Gee, G. W. and Or, D. (2002). Particle size distribution In: methods of soil analysis part 4. Physical methods. Dane, J. H. and Troops, G. C. (eds). Soils Sc. America. Book Series. No. 5 ASA and SSA, Madison, W. L. Pp. 225-293.
- Govers, G., Mevckx, R., Van, Oost, K. and Van We Semeal, B. (2013). Managing soil organic carbon for global benefits: A STAP Technical Report Global Environment Facility, Washington, D. C.
- Hamed, L. M. M., Fouda, S. and Emara, E. R. (2019). Conserving soil fertility and sustaining crop performance via soil tillage systems and crop rotation. Doi: 10.21608/ASEJSAE., 2019, 31624.
- Ibe, O. K. (2014). Characterization, classification and suitability evaluation of soils for crop production along a toposequence in Ohafia, Abia State, Nigeria. M.Sc. thesis submitted to the PG School, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, Abia State, Pp. 120.
- Ibe, O. K. (2021). Spatial analysis of soil carbon sequestration, aggregation and aggregate stability under different parent materials and land uses in southern Nigeria. PhD Dissertation submitted to the Postgraduate school, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, P.420.
- Igwe, C. A. and Ejiofor, N. (2005). Structural stability of exposed gully wall in Central Eastern Nigeria as affected by soil properties. *International Agrophysics*, 19: 215-222.
- Igwe, C. A., Akanigbo, F. O. R. and Mbagwu, J. S. C. (1995). Physical properties of soils of southeastern Nigeria and the role of some aggregating agents in their stability. *Soil Science*. 160(6)114-12.
- IUSS Working Group WRB (2015). World Reference base for soil resources 2014, update 2015 international soil classification system for naming soil and creating system for naming soil and creating legends for soil maps. *World Soil Resources Reports*. No. 106. FAO, Rome.
- Jungerius, P. D. (1964). The soils. In: Soil survey memoir No. 1: The Anambra-Do River Area Government Printers, Enugu. Pp. 1-22.
- Khera, K. L. and Singh, M. J. (2008). Soil erodibility indices under different land uses in lower Shiwaliks. *Tropical Ecology*, 49(9):113-119.
- Lal, R. (2004). Soil C-Sequestration impacts on global climate change and food security. *Science*, 304:1623-1627.

- Lal, R. (2005). Soil carbon sequestration in natural and managed tropical forest ecosystems. *Journal of Sustainable Forestry*. Vol. 21.
- Lal, R. (2017). Soil organic carbon sequestration: importance and state of science. Proceedings of the global symposium on soil organic carbon. 2017 held 21-23rd March, 2017, FAO headquarters, Rome, Italy. Pp. 6-12.
- Lal, R. and Okigbo, B. N. (1990). An assessment of soil degradation in southern Nigeria. *Environment, Working Paper*. World Bank, Washinton D. C. USA.
- Lal, R. U. (2006). *Encyclopedia of soil science*. 1st edition volume 1. Taylor and Francis Group, London.
- Lal, R., Kimbe, J. M., Follet, R. F. and Cole, C. V. (1998). The potential of US Cropland to sequester carbon and mitigate the Greenhouse Effect. Sheeping Bear Press, Inc Chelsea, M. I.
- Lekwa, G. and Oparaugo, H. (1984). Relationship of landscape elements to soil properties and amangement of a pale-udult in the rainforest belt of southeastern Nigeria. Paper presented at the 12th Annual Conference of Soil Science Society of Nigeria, Rivers State University of Science and technology, Port-Harcourt.
- Lekwa, G. and Whiteside, E. P. (1986). Coastal plain sands of southeastern Nigeria: Morphology, classification and genetic relationship. *Soil Science American Journal*, 50:154-160.
- Li, C., Li, Y. and Tan, L. (2010). Soil organic carbon stock and efflux in-deep soil of desert and oasis. *Environment Earth Science*, 60:549-557.
- McLean, E. O. (1982). Soil ph and lime requinena. In: Page, A. L., Miller, R. H. and Keeney, Dr. R. (Eds). *Methods of soil analysis*. Part 2. American Society of Agronomy, Madison, W. I. Pp. 199-224.
- Monanu, P. C. (1975b). Temperature and sunshine. In: Ofomata, G. E. K. (Ed). *Nigeria in Maps: Eastern States*. Benin City, Nigeria. Ethiope Pub. House.
- NDBDA (2019). Research collaboration and training reports, agricultural services, Niger Delta Basin Development Authority, 21 Azikiwe Road, Port-Harcourt, NDBDA/361/vol.1/82.
- Nelson, P. N. and Sommers, L. E. (1982). Total carbon, organic carbon and organic matter In: Page, A. L., Miller, R. H and Keeney, D. R. (Eds). *Methods of soil analysis, Part 3. Chemical Methods ASA and SSSA*, Madison, W. L. pp. 539-579.
- NIMET (2017). Periodic publication, Port Harcourt Station, Port-Harcourt International Airport.
- NIMET (2018). Nigeria climate review bulletin. No. 001, NIMET, Abuja.
- Nnaji, G. U. (2008). Fertility status of some soil in Isoko South Local Government Area of Delta State. Proceedings of the 42nd Annual Conference Agricultural Society of Nigeria

- (ASN). October, 19th 2008. Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki, Nigeria.
- Nuga, B. O. (2009). Classification and evaluation of the soils of Ikwuano Local Government Area, Abia State, Nigeria,. Ph.D. Thesis. Department of University of Ibadan, pp. 191.
- Nuga, B. O. and Akinbola, G. E (2011). Characterization and Classification of Soils Developed over Coastal Plain Sands Shale Parent Materials in Abia State, Nigeria. *Journal Technology and Education in Nigeria (JOTEN)*. Vol. 16.No. 1.Pp. 1- 23.
- Nwagbara, M. O. and Ibe, O. K (2015).Cimate Change and Soil Conditions of the Tropical Rainforest of Southeastern Nigeria.*Journal of Geography and Earth Sciences*.Vol. 3.No. 1.Pp.99-106.
- Nzegbule, E. C. (2018). Many parts yet one earth: agricultural system cannot be an Island. 34 Inaugural lecturer, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike. 16th May, 2018. Pp. 58.
- Obi, I. U. (1986). Statistical method of detecting differences between treatment means. SNAP Press Ltd. Enugu, Nigeria, Pp. 45.
- Odurukwe, S. O., Anuebunwa, F. O., Iloka, A. W., Udealor, A. and Ibedu, M. A. (1995). Phsycial environment, fallow and multi-purpose tree and shrub species in the farming systems of southeast zone of Nigeria.A report of diagnostic survey-NRCRI, Umudike Publications.
- Ofomata, G. E. K. (1975). Nigeria in maps: eastern states. In: G. E. K. Ofomata (Ed). *Vegetation types and soils*.Ethiopia publishing House, Benin, Nigeria. Pp. 30-45.
- Ogumole, J. O., Sharma, B. R., McCartney, M. A., Zemaadim, B. E. and Leta G. (2014). Land use impact on soil physical quality and soil structure in three Highland Watersheds of Ethiopia. *Advances in Plants and Agriculture Research*, 1(4):00019.
- Ojanuga, A. G. (1977). A study of soils and soil genesis in the southeastern upland Nigeria.Phh.D. Dissertation.University of Wisconsin, Madison, WIS USA.
- Ojanuga, A G. (1998).A framework for Nigerian Soil Classification System.Proceedings of the 24th annual conference of the Soil Science Society of Nigeria, Bauchi.Pp10-15.
- Okpamen, S. U., Ilori, E. G., Agho, I., Nkechika, A., Maidoh, F. U. and Okonjo, P. N. (2013).Ibfluence of depths and soil ph on forms of magnesium in soils of four parent materials (rhodic pale udults, rhodic tropudalFs, oxictropudalFs and aqui trossament).*Journal of Soil Science and Environmental Management*, 4(4), 71-76.
- Osodeke, V. E. (2017). Greedy tropical soils: appeasing the hungry soils for sustainable food production. 26th inaugural lecturer.Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, Abia State, Nigeria.Pp. 28.

- Salako, F. K. (2015). For soil to oil the Nation: advancing the frontiers of conservation agriculture in Nigeria. The 48th Inaugural Lecturer. Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, Nigeria. FUNAAB Inaugural lecturer Series No. 48 Wednesday 4th February, 2015. Pp. 168.
- Salako, F. K. (2003). Soil physical conditions in Nigerian savannas and biomass production. Department of Soil Science and Agricultural Mechanization, University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, Nigeria. Lecture given at the College on Soil Physics on 3-21 March, 2003.
- Smith, C. M. (1976). Diagnostic methods. Pages 115-141. In: White, W. C., Collins, D. N. (eds). The fertilizer handbook. The fertilizer Institute, 1015, N. W. Washington, D. C. 20636. Pp. 208.
- Sulieman, M. M. and Algarni, A. M. (2019). Soil Organic carbon mapping and prediction based on depth intervals using Kriging technique: A Case of Study in Alluvial Soil from Sudan. *Eurasian Journal of Soil Science*, 8(1):44-53.
- Thomas, G. W. (1982). Exchangeable cations. In: Page, A. L. (Ed). Methods of soil analysis, Part 2. American Society of Agronomy and Soil Science Society of America, Madison Wisconsin, Pp. 139-165.
- Uguru, M. I., Balyevi, K. P. and Aba, S. C. (2011). Indicators of climate change in the derived savannah rich of Nsukka, Southeastern Nigeria. *Journal of Soil Science*, 18:175-182.
- Ullasa, M. Y. and Kumar, M. D. (2017). Spatial distribution of organic carbon in selected gardens of Karnataka. Society for advancement of human and natural. *International Journal of farm Sciences*, 7(3):28-33.
- Yadav, A. S. and Arora, S. (2018). Crop residue management in diverse agroecosystems for improving soil health- An overview. *Journal of Soil and Water Conservation*, 17(4):387-392.